

**RELATIONS BETWEEN CHEMICAL ACTIVITY AND ABSORPTION IN THE
ULTRAVIOLET OF CERTAIN ORGANIC MOLECULES. PART III. THE
VELOCITY OF REPLACEMENT OF THE CHLORINE ATOMS IN
THE CHLORO DERIVATIVES OF THE SUBSTITUTED
AMIDES OF MALONIC ACID**

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This study was undertaken to correlate the chemical activity of some chloro derivatives of the substituted amides of malonic acid as expressed by the velocity of replacement of their chlorine atoms with their absorption in the ultraviolet, and to investigate the factors that govern the velocity of replacement of chlorine. It has been found that (1) the curves for the velocity are in general agreement with those of absorption in the ultraviolet, (2) the velocity is augmented by the presence of methyl group in benzene nucleus, (3) the chlorine atoms of the dichloro derivatives are replaced in succession, and (4) the aliphatic straight chain attached to the carbonyl groups increases the rate of replacement.

A study of the chemical activity of the substances mentioned in Table I, was undertaken to correlate this phase of chemical activity of the molecules with their absorption in the ultraviolet. These investigations were undertaken in order to examine how far the velocity of replacement of the chlorine atoms is related to the nature and position of the groups attached to the carbonyl radicles, between which the $-CCl_2$ -complex is situated.

If it may be suggested that all the four valencies of the carbon atom are not equal in their intensity with regard to the holding on of the groups attached to them, in a molecule of the type :—

the tenacity with which the chlorine atoms are held by valency (1) and (2) may not be equal, in which case it is possible that when the chlorine atom attached by valency (1) is removed, the velocity of the removal of the second chlorine atom held by (2) may be much lowered down. This could be attributed either (a) to the difference in intensity with which the carbon holds the two chlorine atoms, or (b) to the fact that when one of the chlorine atoms is removed, the conditions of the original molecule may undergo such a change that the chemical activity of the molecule as measured by the velocity of the replacement of the second chlorine may be profoundly altered. For this purpose a study of the velocity of replacement of chlorine atoms by hydrogen atoms was undertaken. The chloro compounds were reduced by hydriodic acid (Kurt Meyer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 951, 305). The reaction is represented as

25 C.c. of the solution of the dichloro compound containing 0.01 g. mol. per litre were mixed in a flask with 10 c.c. of 7.5% potassium iodide solution to which 5 c.c. of hydrochloric acid (d 1.16) were added. A battery of 10 such flasks was simultaneously heated under reflux in a water-bath maintained at 100°. At the end of each interval of fifteen minutes, one of the flasks was removed from the bath and cooled by immersing in ice-cold water to arrest the reaction. The iodine liberated was then immediately titrated by 0.0477 *N*-sodium thiosulphate solution.

Fig. 1 represents the curves for the velocity of replacement of chlorine in (1) dichloro-malon-diphenylamide, (2) dichloro-malon-di-*p*-tolylamide, (3) dichloro-malon-di-*m*-chlorotolyl-

amide, (4) dichloromalon-di-*o*-tolylamide, (5) dichloromalon-di-*i*:*o*:*o*:*o*-xylylidide, (6) dichloromalon-di-*p*-chloronaphthylamide.

TABLE I

Names of compounds.	D = Dichloromalon.						C = Chloromethylchloromalon.					
	h.m.	h.m.	h.m.	h.m.	h.m.	h.m.	h.m.	h.m.	h.m.	h.m.	h.m.	
D-diphenylamide	0'15	0'30	0'45	1'0	1'15	1'30	1'45	2'0	2'15	2'30	2'45	
D-di- <i>p</i> -tolylamide	10'17	19'56	27'67	34'11	40'30	44'84	48'42	51'75	54'85	57'24	59'86	
D-di- <i>o</i> -tolylamide	11'45	20'03	28'14	34'58	41'02	45'79	49'13	52'23	55'10	57'95	61'05	
D- <i>m</i> -chlorotolylamide	9'63	18'84	27'67	34'10	40'30	45'17	50'08	53'18	56'04	58'91	...	
D-di- <i>o</i> -tolylamide	14'40	27'66	39'59	48'89	53'45	58'20	62'96	67'02	69'88	71'55	73'46	
D-di- <i>i</i> : <i>o</i> : <i>o</i> : <i>o</i> -xylylidide	14'79	28'38	40'30	51'04	57'58	63'68	67'73	71'07	73'22	74'74	76'56	
D-di- <i>β</i> -naphthylamide	5'72	10'73	15'63	20'03	23'62	27'31	30'53	33'87	37'20	40'54	...	
D-diheptylamide	14'79	34'82	44'82	54'14	59'15	64'16	69'64	72'50	75'13	77'27	79'18	
D-dipropylamide	10'49	24'56	35'77	41'38	48'65	52'95	58'08	62'59	66'30	70'36	...	
D-dibenzylamide	10'02	20'75	30'87	41'50	48'65	54'85	60'58	63'57	66'66	69'16	71'35	
D-dichlorophenylamide	12'88	25'04	33'87	40'54	45'31	49'30	51'99	53'90	54'85	55'37	56'04	
D-mono- <i>β</i> -tolylamide	11'68	21'46	30'29	37'21	42'69	46'31	46'74	48'41	49'30	50'08	51'27	
C-diphenylamide	8'11	16'69	25'28	32'91	38'16	41'97	46'27	50'89	51'52	54'38	56'73	
C-di- <i>β</i> -tolylamide	6'68	12'40	17'17	20'99	24'80	29'33	31'96	34'82	36'73	37'68	38'64	
C-di- <i>o</i> -tolylamide	1'43	4'77	7'63	10'02	12'40	14'07	15'74	17'17	17'68	18'13	18'60	

It is seen from a comparison of the curves in Fig. 1 of this part with those in Fig. 1 of part I of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 28, 421) that the velocity of replacement of the chlorine atoms and the absorption in the ultraviolet are in general agreement. In the order of the increasing velocity of replacement of chlorine atoms, the substances can be arranged as 1, 4, 3, 2, 5 (*vide* Table I).

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

In this connection a corresponding order is also noticed in the absorption spectra of the same substances. It has also been observed that on the whole the velocity of replacement of chlorine atom by hydrogen atom is augmented by the presence of a methyl group in the benzene nucleus. Further, the position of the methyl group in the nucleus also exerts a considerable influence on the velocity of replacement of the chlorine atoms.

Another point of interest which emerges out is the fact that in each case the velocity of replacement is considerably lowered when 50% of the total chlorine are reduced.

For example, in the case of dichloromalon-diphenylamide, during first fortyfive minutes 27.67% of chlorine are reduced; whereas after two hours (when almost 50% of chlorine are already reduced during next fortyfive minutes) only 8.11% are reduced ($59.86 - 51.75 = 8.11$). This is borne out by the nature of the curve (1) in Fig 1. A closer reference to Table I will reveal that such behaviour is exhibited by all substances.

Further both the chlorine atoms in a compound like $-RNHCO'CCl_2CONHR-$ do not seem to be replaced simultaneously by hydrogen atoms. As a matter of fact the mechanism of the replacement could be represented as

That the chlorine atoms are not simultaneously removed is borne out by the following considerations:—

(1) If the chlorine atoms were replaced simultaneously there would not have been a big drop in the velocity of replacement after 50% of the total chlorine had been reduced.

(2) That the interaction of these dichloro compounds with phenylhydrazine takes place in two distinct stages, wherein the chlorine atom is removed in succession (*vide* Part IV of this series).

In Fig. 2 are traced the curves (1) dichloromalon-diheptylamide, (2) dichloromalon-dipropylamide, and (3) dichloromalon-dibenzylamide.

These curves explicitly indicate that when the radicals attached to the carbonyl groups carry aliphatic straight chain, the velocity of replacement of chlorine is increased (*vide* curve 1, Fig 2). If the chain is shorter, the velocity is decreased (*vide* curve, 2, Fig 2). It is also decreased when the radical is in the form of a cyclic structure with the same number of carbon atoms (*vide* curve 3 which has the same number of carbon atoms as in curve 1).

FIG. 3

2-1450P-11

FIG. 4

Here, again, the agreement between the curves expressing the velocity of replacement of the chlorine atoms by hydrogen and the curves expressing the absorption in the ultraviolet is excellent (*cf.* Fig. 3, part I of this series, *loc. cit.*, p. 423).

In Fig. 3 are drawn the curves for the velocity of replacement (1) dichloromalon-mono-chlorophenylamide, and (2) dichloromalon-mono-*p*-tolylamide. These curves show a curious drop in the velocity of replacement of chlorine atoms due to the presence of only one heavy radical in this case, as compared with the corresponding malonamides.

In Fig. 4 are drawn the curves for the velocity of replacement of chlorine atoms in compounds (1) chloromethyl-chloromalon-diphenylamide, (2) chloromethylchloromalon-di-*p*-tolylamide, and (3) chloromethylchloromalon-di-*o*-tolylamide.

The remarkable decrease in the velocity of replacement of chlorine atoms of these chloro derivatives may be attributed to the presence of the $-ClH_2C$ -grouping.

It may finally be pointed out that there is a close agreement between the curves expressing the velocity of replacement of chlorine atoms (*vide* Figs. 1-4 in this part) and the curves showing the absorption in the ultraviolet in the case of the same substances so far studied (*vide* Figs. 1, 2, 3 and 4, Part I of this series, *loc. cit.*).

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